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East African Terrorism Landscape

Al-Shabaab, an Al-Qaeda affiliate, Sunni Islamic terrorist group briefly gained control of central and southern Somalia in 2011.¹ The group became formally recognized as a foreign terrorist group in 2008. Al-Shabaab targets foreign military forces, the Somali government and security forces, and civilian targets such as schools, shopping malls, universities, and busy intersections. The group has carried out mass-casualty operations in Kenya, Somalia, and Uganda, but has never conducted an attack outside East Africa.² Al-Shabab is estimated to have up to 7,000 to 12,000 fighters, almost double the number it had three years ago.³ Al-Shabaab recruits foreign fighters from the Middle East, and Somalis in neighboring countries but also Somalis in Western countries like the United States, United Kingdom, Australia, and Sweden.⁴ Utilizing the internet they exploit grievances, glorify returning to Somalia, and often antagonize the West in their recruitment strategies.

The top-level actors of Al Shabaab include the leader Ahmed Diriye, his deputy Abukar Ali Adan, and the financial chief commander Mahad Karate. Other than the main leaders Al Shabaab has An executive council, known as the *shura*, believed to be made up of around a dozen members and is the main decision-making body when it comes to attacks.⁵ The group also operates multiple security organs, including the Amniyat, an intelligence agency with some

¹Somalia Situation Update | ACLED

²Foreign Terrorist Organization; Al-Shabaab

³Al-Shabaab whetting sword near the Border of Ethiopia

⁴Omenma et al. Al-Shabaab and Boko Haram: Recruitment Strategies

⁵Klobucista et al. Al-Shabaab

policing responsibility, and Jeysh Al-Hisbah, al Shabaab's police force.⁶ Amniyat, for example, leads counterintelligence efforts and purges Al-Shabaab fighters suspected of spying for state intelligence agencies. This illustrates Al-Shabaab's status as a comprehensive organization equipped with the technical capabilities, personnel, and expertise necessary to operate with minimal risk or threat to its survival.

Speaking of Al-Shabaab's survival, there is another terrorist organization operating in East Africa; the Islamic State in Somalia Province (ISSP) which was formed by a group of defectors from Al-Shabaab, pledged allegiance to ISIS in October 2015, and gained recognition as an official province in 2018. 'ISSP adheres to ISIS's strict interpretation of Islamic law and aims to extend ISIS's self-proclaimed caliphate in Africa'.⁷ These regional terrorist groups differ in their goals because Al-Qaeda aims to establish Islamic governments by overthrowing corrupt regimes in the Middle East, considering the United States as the main obstacle. By targeting the US, they seek to force its withdrawal from the region, making the regimes vulnerable. Despite viewing Shi'a Muslims as apostates, Al-Qaeda refrains from openly opposing sectarianism due to its popularity among many Muslims, despite recognizing it as wasteful and harmful to their broader jihadist goals. The Islamic State differs from Al-Qaeda by focusing on a "near enemy" strategy, targeting regional "apostate" regimes such as those in Syria and Iraq, instead of the United States. Baghdadi, like his predecessors, prioritizes purifying the Islamic community by attacking Shi'a, religious minorities, and rival jihadist groups as part of this strategy.⁸ Therefore these two forces are not friends or collaborators by any means and according to AQ's strategy

⁶ Ibid

⁷Foreign Terrorist Organization | ISIS Somalia

⁸ Byman, Comparing Al-Qaeda and ISIS

globally, its affiliates since 2015 have sought to crack down on rival “provinces”, which has meant that Al-Shabaab is determined to eliminate ISSP.

The ISSP and Al-Shabaab extend their support to other groups, for example, ISSP al-Sudani (ISSP fighter in Puntland killed by US Seal Team earlier in 2023) not only operated in Somalia, “but also financed and masterminded operations for the other so-called Islamic State (IS) provinces in Congo and Mozambique and even as far as Afghanistan. (Jacob Zenn)” Similarly, Al Shabaab has grown so much to the point that rather than AQ Central supporting Al-Shabaab, now Al-Shabaab reportedly supports AQ with funding from its coffers in Somalia. As much as their influence Alshabaab is way bigger in manpower, annual revenue, territory of control, and organization strategy. Al-Shabaab does not have a rival group in East Africa; they are the dominant group in the region and no evidence shows the potential opportunity of other groups growing because Al-Shabaab does not tolerate any other organization affiliates. That being said both organizations are being cracked down on the counterterrorism efforts that have been put in place earlier in 2023. For example, Al-shabaab has lost

Al-Shabaab generates an estimated annual revenue of \$100 million by coercing various businesses and communities to comply with the Zakat system (2.5% tax on annual assets).⁹ To enforce this system, the group employs multiple layers of governance. They meticulously record individuals' annual assets to determine the appropriate taxation amounts. Additionally, the Amniyat (policing forces), serve as tax collectors, ensuring consistent collection of Zakat. This approach lends a semblance of legitimacy and credibility to their tax collection methods.¹⁰

⁹ Wendy, Reclaiming Al Shabaab's Revenue

¹⁰Ibid

In addition, Al-Shabaab leverages various revenue sources by exploiting shipping imports and real estate transactions to generate income. Employing intelligence tactics and the threat of violence, the group coerces business owners into paying a share of their assets. For instance, they bomb main travel routes, compelling merchants and civilians to use alternative roads where Al-Shabaab sets up taxation checkpoints.¹¹ Additionally, the group is able to instill fear in business owners by implying control over key commercial routes like Bosaso and Mogadishu, even if they don't physically govern these areas. Moreover, Al-Shabaab also invests some of its income in land and medium-sized businesses outside their controlled territories.¹² They specifically target areas beyond their control to avoid influencing their properties with their taxing policies due to the economic instability in their controlled zones.

Al-Shabaab is very particular about its revenue because a good portion of it streams to support its estimated 7,000 to 12,000 fighters. They employ diverse means to extract money from civilians, with government officials as a primary target. However, because officials have no reason to comply with the 2.5% zakat system, Al-Shabaab resorts to different tactics. Al Shabaab has been accused of having pressured clan elders to nominate sympathetic candidates to run for office, thereby giving them inside access to the National Assembly, Senate, and state legislatures.¹³ They use that information to extort money from government officials.

Apart from taxation and extortion, Al-Shabaab's assets also encompass their amassed ammunition. Alshabaab has been engaged in years of arms smuggling into the country, including via Puntland and Yemen. They also have accumulated weapons and gear gained from attacks on military installations stored in Al-Shabaab, a stockpile of increasingly sophisticated weaponry.¹⁴

¹¹Ibid

¹²Ibid

¹³Ibid

¹⁴Ibid

Additionally, their focus on IEDs which they use in most attacks contributes to their arsenal. This secure stockpile of armaments enables Al-Shabaab to monopolize violence, facilitating tax collection in their controlled territories. Without these resources, the organization would struggle to secure weapons, pay its personnel, and maintain influence in the communities they control.

Al-Shabaab's operations heavily rely on guerrilla tactics and asymmetric warfare strategies, predominantly utilizing skirmishes and small arms fire (23%), assassination and murder (11%), and IED detonations (11%) as their preferred methods of attack.¹⁵ The group also employs suicide bombers and suicide vehicle-borne improvised explosive devices (VBIEDs), especially within Somalia, exploiting the relative ease of moving explosives within a country compared to crossing borders where such materials are more detectable. The intensity of attacks has noticeably increased, by a 14% rise in civilian casualties from explosive violence in Somalia in 2019 compared to 2018.¹⁶ The deadliest attacks in Somalia occurred between 2017 and 2019. One of those attacks was the two truck bombings that took place in Mogadishu, on 14 October 2017, killing at least 587 people and injuring 316 others.¹⁷ There is an alleged correlation between the recent increase of Al-Shabaab targeting civilians and the escalated US airstrikes against Al-Shabaab after President Donald Trump extended the campaign against Al-Shabaab which permitted increasing the rate of airstrikes against them. These attacks on civilians could serve as a display of Al-Shabaab's strength, sending a message to the US that they remain potent and capable of carrying out assaults such as these.¹⁸ It might also be an attempt to provoke the Somali Government into reacting to the US airstrikes or urging for their cessation due to the significant losses inflicted within the country.

¹⁵Pattni, The threat of Al-Shabaab to Somalia in 2019

¹⁶Platts-Dunn, Al-Shabaab and increasing civilian harm in Somalia

¹⁷Al-Shabaab's Attacks in East Africa: A Timeline | Crisisgroup

¹⁸Platts-Dunn, Al-Shabaab and increasing civilian harm in Somalia

It is important to note that Al-Shabaab conducts attacks both within Somalia's borders and beyond, which reflects on their recruitment capabilities and strategic planning. For example, the Garissa University College assault in Kenya in April 2015¹⁹ and the September 2015 Jaanle forward operating bases (FOB) attack²⁰ exemplify this dual approach. When fighting peacekeeping missions, Al-Shabaab employs Explosive Devices (IEDs) and follows with significant infantry assaults on FOBs. Targeting FOBs is pivotal for Al-Shabaab, allowing them to replenish light weapons and ammunition, indicating an escalation in their attacks. Their strategy typically involves multiple waves of assaults during FOB attacks. The head of 'ATMIS estimated that between 2007 and 2022, over 3,500 peacekeepers had lost their lives on the mission, rendering Somalia the deadliest peace operations theater worldwide'.²¹

The most recent counter-terrorism initiative was issued in June 2023, Operation Black Lion, which consists of collaboration between Somalia's forces and non-ATMIS units from Kenya, Djibouti, and Ethiopia. This joint effort symbolizes a unified front against the Al-Shabaab threat, aiming to restore peace and stability in Somalia by liberating the remaining territories under Al-Shabaab control.²² Some of the progress of the operation is that the Somali government has reclaimed more territory from Al-Shabaab in a shorter time than it had in the past five years combined.²³ Additionally, there have been numerous suspected US airstrikes targeting Al-Shabaab positions in Mudug, Shabeelow, and Dumaaye, resulting in the elimination of hundreds of militants.²⁴ The ground clashes of Operation Black Lion forces have inflicted severe setbacks on Al-Shabaab. The local support for the government's campaign has been

¹⁹Al-Shabaab's Attacks in East Africa: A Timeline | Crisisgroup

²⁰Williams, Conventional Insurgents

²¹Ibid

²²Operation Black Lion | Mogadisho24

²³Zenn, Al-Shabaab Versus the Islamic State in Somalia Province

²⁴Somalia Situation Update | ACLED

remarkably crucial to the operation's success. In response, Al-Shabaab has resorted to attacking local officials to discourage further support for the government's efforts.

The Black Lion operation coincides with the withdrawal of ATMIS (African Union Transition Mission in Somalia) forces from Somalia.²⁵ This occurrence, viewed positively, signifies a significant step towards greater self-reliance.²⁶ However, it involves two independent variables: the simultaneous transfer of ATMIS forces and the Black Lion operation. This presents a risk to Somalia's aim of sustaining peace in the future, as it might become unclear whether the departure of ATMIS or the Black Lion operation compelled Al-Shabaab's retreat.²⁷ Counterterrorism efforts must prioritize civilian security, as they often find themselves caught amidst these conflicting violent forces. In the case of Somalia, I recommend that following a government's engagement with a local community for intelligence or support in their campaign, they provide the utmost protection to prevent retaliation by terrorist groups. This not only safeguards the community but also bolsters the government's campaign and fosters trust between the government and the community, aligning with the broader objective of counterterrorism.

Regarding recommendations, my initial suggestion involves the US campaign against Al-Shabaab, which has been effective in significantly reducing the group's numbers. However, it's crucial to acknowledge the potential damage, particularly civilian casualties, which undermines the efficacy of counterterrorism efforts. Precision becomes pivotal in such procedures; a single unintended casualty might inadvertently bolster support for the very terrorists being fought against. Notably, the Black Lion operation has demonstrated effectiveness by dismantling Al-Shabaab's physical control over territories, disrupting their tax collection,

²⁵African Union Rejects Somalia's | Somali Guardian

²⁶Security Council Speakers Highlight Somalia's Progress | UN Press

²⁷Ibid

training camps, and radicalization activities. Sequential implementation of these counterterrorism strategies proves essential, allowing both the country and international supporters to discern effective measures from ineffective ones. Additionally, securing borders between Kenya, Somalia, and Ethiopia emerges as a critical next step to prevent Al-Shabaab from seeking refuge in the countryside of these nations and establishing new safe havens.

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